

THE MAGNETIC STUDY OF PERIODATES. PART II. THE STRUCTURE OF PERIODATES OF SODIUM, SILVER, MERCURY AND LANTHANUM

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The magnetic susceptibilities of the periodates of Na, Ag, Hg and La have been determined. Experimental values χ_M have been compared with the χ_M calculated from the theoretically possible formulae of these periodates. From this comparison definite conclusions regarding the structure of these periodates have been arrived at.

In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 158) one of us reported the magnetic susceptibilities of periodic acid in the solid state and in solutions of different concentrations with a view to ascertaining its constitution. The χ_M of the acid in the solid state and in its solutions are almost equal and it was shown that the acid existed as $\text{HIO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. This paper deals with the magnetic susceptibilities of some metallic periodates which correspond to a number of periodic acids derived from the union of different molecules of water with the hypothetical I_2O_7 molecule as shown below.

TABLE I

Hypothetical I_2O_7 with	Formula of the acid.	Name of the acid.	Salts known.
$7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	H_7IO_7	Orthoperiodic acid	No salt known
$6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{H}_{12}\text{I}_2\text{O}_{13}$	Diorthoperiodic acid	$\text{Zr}_3\text{I}_2\text{O}_{13} \cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$
$5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	H_5IO_6	Paraperiodic acid	Ag_5IO_6
$4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{H}_9\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}$	Diparaperiodic acid	$\text{Li}_9\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
$3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	H_3IO_5	Mesoperiodic acid	Ag_3IO_5
$2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{H}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_9$	Dimesoperiodic acid	$\text{Ag}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_9$
H_2O	HIO_4	Metaperiodic acid	KIO_4 , NaIO_4 , etc.

The structure of these metallic periodates is still a matter of some speculation. From analytical results it is not possible to say whether a particular periodate is a hydrated salt of one acid or acid salt of another. Thus for example the periodate of the composition $2\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{I}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ can either be secondary sodium paraperiodate $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$ or sodium dimesoperiodate $\text{Na}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_9 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The magnetic susceptibility determinations of some periodates have now been undertaken with a view to discussing their structures. χ_m of these periodates have been calculated theoretically and compared with the experimental values. From this comparison definite conclusions regarding the structures of periodates have been arrived at.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pure 'Analar' salts were used in the preparation of periodates :

1. *Secondary sodium paraperiodate* was prepared by the method of Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1088). The precipitate was repeatedly washed to free it from iodide, chloride and iodate. (Found : Na, 16.67 ; I, 46.80 ; O₂, 20.1. Na₂H₃IO₆ requires Na, 16.91 ; I, 46.69 ; O₂, 20.58 per cent) according to the decomposition :

2. *Silver mesoperiodate* was prepared by the method of Wells (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1901, 26, 278). (Found : Ag, 61.2 ; I, 24.1 ; O₂, 14.9. Ag₃IO₆ requires Ag, 61.0 ; I, 23.84 ; O₂, 14.87 per cent) according to the equation

3. *Diargentous paraperiodate* was prepared by adding Na₂H₃IO₆ in dilute nitric acid to a solution of AgNO₃ and filtering. The filtrate on cooling gave a crop of yellow crystals of Ag₂H₃IO₆. (Found : Ag, 44.8 ; I, 29.3 ; O₂, 16.2. Ag₂H₃IO₆ requires Ag, 48.86 ; I, 28.73 ; O₂, 16.28 per cent) according to the decomposition

4. *Mercuric diparaperiodate* was prepared by adding Na₂H₃IO₆ in dilute nitric acid to a solution of Hg(NO₃)₂. (Found : Hg, 65.7 ; I, 20.92 ; O₂, 14.03. Hg₂I₂O₁₁ requires Hg, 65.5 ; I, 20.72 ; O₂, 14.28 per cent).

5. *Dihydrated lanthanum mesoperiodate* was prepared by the addition of Na₂H₃IO₆ in dilute nitric acid to lanthanum nitrate solution. The salt was obtained as a white powder. (Found : La, 35.32 ; I, 36.5 ; O₂, 13.32. Calc. for LaIO₆.2H₂O : La, 35.07 ; I, 36.33 ; O₂, 12.57 per cent) according to decomposition

Susceptibility Determinations.

The susceptibilities were determined by the modified Guoy's method (Nevgi, *Current Sci.*, 1935, 4, 403). Conductivity water ($\kappa = 0.72 \times 10^{-6}$) was used as the reference substance and the method was standardised by making determinations on compounds of known

values of susceptibility. The results of known substances with % error are reported in Table II and susceptibility values of periodates in Table III.

TABLE II

Substance.	Susceptibility $\times 10^6$		Error.
	Mean of three readings.	Reported value.	
1. KCl	0.514	0.516	0.2%
2. Naphthalene	0.719	0.717	0.3
3. Trinitrobenzene	0.350	0.352	0.3
4. Camphoric anhydride	0.624	0.622	0.3
5. Ethyl alcohol	0.743	0.744	0.1

TABLE III

Substance.	Susceptibility	
	per g. (mean of three readings).	per mol.
1. Disodium paraperiodate	0.257×10^{-6}	69.9
2. Silver mesoperiodate	0.233	123.64
3. Diargentous paraperiodate	0.2256	99.66
4. Mercuric diparaperiodate	0.1828	225.55
5. Dihydrated lanthanum mesoperiodate	0.1591	60.76

DISCUSSION

The molecular susceptibility of a polar salt may be considered as the sum of the susceptibilities of its ions.

$$\chi_{\text{salt}} = \chi_{\text{cation}} + \chi_{\text{anion}}$$

The ionic susceptibilities have been derived by a number of different methods and also from theoretical considerations (Miss Trew, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1941, 37, 476). The average value for Na^+ is 6.8×10^{-6} . The hydrogen ion is generally considered to have zero ionic susceptibility in the solid acids. Miss Trew (*loc. cit.*) has suggested a method for calculating the ionic susceptibility of metaperiodic acid ion (IO_4) from IO_3 as follows:

Ionic susceptibility of IO_4 = (Ionic susceptibility of IO_3 + susceptibility of 4O)—depression due to I—O bond:

The depression of diamagnetism was calculated to be -4.33 units by comparing the atomic susceptibility for 3 oxygen atoms with the values obtained by subtracting the ionic susceptibility of I⁺ ion from that of IO_3 ion. The value of IO_4 ion calculated is -51.7 . This value is in excellent agreement with the experimental value -51.8 (reported by Aggarwal and Singh, *loc. cit.*). This also agrees within experimental error with Kido's value of -53.4 .

The above simple method for calculating ionic susceptibility of IO_4 ion can be extended to other oxyhalogen ions. The ionic susceptibilities of IO_4 , IO_3 , IO_2 and I_2O_7 ions are calculated as below:

Calculation of ionic susceptibility of IO_4 ion.*

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_{\text{IO}_3} &= -51.6 \\ \chi_{\text{I}} &= -50.8 \end{aligned}$$

for 3 oxygen atoms	—	-0.8
Pascal's value for three oxygen atoms	—	-13.8
Depression due to 3(I—O) bonds	—	-13.8—(-0.8)=-13
Depression due to I—O bond	—	-13/3=-4.33

Therefore ionic susceptibility of IO_4 ion =

$$\begin{aligned} &(\chi_{\text{I}} + \text{susceptibility of 4 oxygen atoms}) - \text{depression due to 4(I—O) bonds} \\ &= [(-50.8) + (-18.4) - (-17.3)] = -51.7 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly ionic susceptibilities of IO_3 and IO_2 ions are calculated as -51.97 and -52.24 respectively.

Ionic susceptibility of I_2O_9 ion.— I_2O_9 can be represented by the formula

I_2O_9 can be split into two portions IO_3 and IO_4 ions and there is only one I—O bond connecting the two portions.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hence the ionic susceptibility of } \text{I}_2\text{O}_9 &= \chi_{\text{IO}_3} + \chi_{\text{IO}_4} - \text{depression due to I—O bond} \\ &= (-51.97 - 51.7) - (-4.33) = -99.32. \end{aligned}$$

It is now possible to derive the structure of metallic disodium paraperiodate which corresponds to two salts of the possible periodic acids, i.e., either it can be $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_2\text{IO}_9$ or $\text{Na}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_9 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The molecular susceptibilities of these are calculated by adding the susceptibilities of ions as below.

TABLE IV

Calculations of $\chi_{\text{MNa}_2\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6}$	Calculations of $\chi_{\text{MNa}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_9 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}}$
$\chi_{2\text{Na}^+}$ ions = -13.6	$\chi_{4\text{Na}^+}$ ions = -27.20
χ_{IO_3} ions = -52.4	$\chi_{\text{I}_2\text{O}_9}$ ions = -99.32
χ_{H} ions = 0	$\chi_{3\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ = -38.94
$\chi_{\text{MNa}_2\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6}$ = -65.84	$\chi_{\text{MNa}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_9 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ = -165.46

It is therefore clear that sodium periodate has the formula shown above and the small difference of -4.06 being due to the depression of the bonds connecting two atoms of sodium and IO_3 ion.

* Susceptibility values are expressed in units of 10^{-6} .

Periodates of Silver

(a) *Silver mesoperiodate*, Ag_3IO_5 .—It has got only one formula. Susceptibility of Ag_3IO_5 is calculated as shown below.

$\chi_{3\text{Ag ions}}$	=	- 75
$\chi_{\text{IO}_5 \text{ ion}}$	=	- 51.96
Calculated Ag_3IO_5	=	-126.95
Experimental Ag_3IO_5	=	-123.64

The difference between experimental and the calculated values (-3.31) is probably due to the depression caused by the bonds joining 3Ag and IO_5 ions or due to a small discrepancy in the calculated values of IO_5 ion.

(b) *Diargentous paraperiodate*, $\text{Ag}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$.—It has got two simple formulae (i) $\text{Ag}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$ (diargentous paraperiodate) and (ii) $\text{Ag}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_9 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (silver dimesoperiodate).

TABLE V

Calculations of χ_M for two formulae

Calculated χ_M $\text{Ag}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$		Calculated χ_M $\text{Ag}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_9 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$			
2Ag ions	=	- 50.00	4Ag ions	=	-100.0
IO_5 ion	=	- 52.24	I_2O_9 ion	=	- 99.32
3H ions	=	- 0	$3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	=	- 39.00
$\text{Ag}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$	=	-102.24	$\text{Ag}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_9 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	=	-238.32

The experimental value -99.66 agrees with -102.24 for $\text{Ag}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$. As stated above the small difference of -2.58 between calculated and experimental values may be attributed to the bonds joining Ag and IO_5 ions. The difference -2.58 nearly agrees with the difference -3.31 between calculated and experimental values of Ag_3IO_5 , thus lending further confirmation to these formulae.

Another important case from the structural point of view is that of lanthanum periodate which can have two simple formulae (i) $\text{LaIO}_5 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (dihydrated lanthanum paraperiodate) and (ii) $\text{La}_2\text{H}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (trihydrated lanthanum mesoperiodate).

The value of I_2O_{11} ion can be derived from the experimental χ_M of $\text{Hg}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}$. Substituting the value of Hg^{++} (-37) in $\text{Hg}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11}$ (-225.55) we get the value of I_2O_{11} ion = -77.55.

La^{+++} has 54 extranuclear electrons and just precedes the rare earth elements on the periodic table. Its spectroscopic state 1s_0 , with values of $L=0$, $S=0$ and $j=0$ shows that the ion has zero or extremely weak diamagnetic moment. However, the ion shows a variation of moment with the chemical combination. In some salts such as LaCl_3 it behaves as paramagnetic while in others as $\text{La}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ it is diamagnetic. Its contribution to diamagnetism is so small that it can be easily neglected.

Ignoring the ionic susceptibility contributions of La^{+++} ion, we can compare the experimental and calculated values for the two formulae of lanthanum periodate.

TABLE VI

Formula	Obs.	Calc.	Diff.
(a) $\text{LaIO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	-60.76	-77.95	-17.19
(b) $\text{La}_2\text{H}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$-60.76 \times 2 = -121.52$	-116.55	+ 4.97

The difference in formula (ii) is small but is positive while in other periodates previously discussed it is negative, and equal to -3 or -4 units. Thus the calculated value for formula (ii) is 7 or 10 units less than expected. These 10 units may be attributed to the ionic susceptibility of 2La^{+++} ions. This small contribution of La^{+++} , if considered in formula (i), would tend to increase the difference of -17.19 still further, while for the formula (ii) it would tend to bring the experimental and calculated values still closer. This lends support to the formula $\text{La}_2\text{H}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for lanthanum periodate.

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